

UP-SCALING USING HAAR WAVELETS

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ABSTRACT

The concept of up-scaling is one of the major topics in the simulation of geological systems and subsurface reservoirs. Coarsening provides the link between very detailed geologically accurate models and computationally tractable models on which fluid flow simulations can be performed.

The main requirement of a coarsening method is that it preserves heterogeneity, which is found on length scales spanning various orders of magnitude, and that it is computationally efficient. The technique presented here is a block renormalization scheme in which Haar wavelets are used to separate data averages from fluctuations. A Haar wavelet transform is applied to Darcy's equation in a finite-differences scheme. By transforming the terms in the flow equation we can define new variables in which pressure averages and fluctuations are decoupled. We can then perform a mean-field approximation obtaining a solution to the coarse scale problem which is a good approximation to the averaged fine scale pressure profile.

An attempt to apply the method to two-phase flow equations is made and ideas to extend the technique to irregular grids are examined.

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate dynamic models of subsurface reservoirs have become a necessity in the management of both water resources and waste deposits. The common problem in these two fields is the characterization of the porous medium and of the fluid flow within the system in terms of rock properties such as permeability [Bear, 1972].

One of the most important issues in the study of flow in porous media is the large variability in permeability occurring across multiple scales. Hence the need for the definition of effective properties to be associated with regions of the medium.

A vast number of contributions have been made to clarify whether it is physically meaningful to define such single values and moreover whether a similar approach can be adopted to coarsen the obtained models [Renard and deMarsily, 1997]. The difficulty lies in the inherent dependence of the effective properties on the boundary conditions which cannot be avoided given the constraints that reality imposes on mathematical concepts [Rubin and Gomez-Hernandez, 1990].

In the present paper it will be assumed that a discrete reservoir model exists on what we will refer to as the fine scale and we will attempt to calculate the permeabilities of the corresponding coarse model. The technique is a local renormalization scheme which

emerges from a mean-field treatment of Darcy's equation expressed in finite difference formalism. The resulting permeability map is such that the coarse pressure field reproduces the average of the fine scale pressure profile within errors.

In Section 2 a brief overview of the main concepts behind renormalization and Haar wavelets will be given. The coarsening method from *Pancaldi et al.* [2006] will be summarized in Section 3 together with the results of numerical simulations on synthetic data sets. Finally, in Section 4 the method will be applied to the advection equation, as a very simple model of two-phase flow. The conclusion will present possible extensions to the current work.

2. REAL SPACE RENORMALIZATION AND HAAR WAVELETS

2.1. Real space renormalization and up-scaling. The concept of real space renormalization, first suggested by *Kadanoff* [1966], has proved to be particularly useful in the quest for a coarsening method able to deal with very heterogeneous systems in a limited computational time. The basic idea is to move from the fine description to the coarse model performing the coarsening step by step, progressively incorporating features on larger and larger scales [*King*, 1989].

Applying this framework to one-phase flow in porous media, the permeability of each coarse cell, which we will call "block", is a function of the permeability of the constitutive cells. The choice of function will determine the properties of the coarsening method obtained. One of the most common renormalization schemes emerges from an analogy between permeability and conductance in a system of resistors [*King*, 1989], where the effective permeability of a block in a particular direction corresponds to the equivalent conductance of the corresponding resistor mesh. The coarsening procedure is extremely fast, the computational time scaling linearly in the system size, and can be repeated until a model of the required level of detail is obtained. The speed of the method makes it suitable for the generation of multiple realizations, an invaluable tool for the assessment of uncertainty in the model prediction.

The main drawbacks of this kind of method derive from the basic underlying assumptions, which do not hold in the presence of very strong heterogeneity in the permeability field. Namely, no-flow boundary conditions are imposed at the top and bottom of each block and the pressure is assumed to be constant at the left and right boundaries. The recent literature presents innumerable global up-scaling methods which deal with these issues and provide more accurate coarsening procedures [*Durlouky*, 1991]. However, the strength of local up-scaling methods is in the ease of applicability which make them comparable to the simple averaging schemes that are still the most popular in industry. Although harmonic, arithmetic and geometric means provide exact results only in special cases [*Renard and deMarsily*, 1997], the uncertainty which dominates our understanding of the reservoir structure at all levels is likely to be the dominating factor in the accuracy of our models [*Christie and Blunt*, 2001].

The main trend in the field of coarsening is towards multilevel up-scaling, see for example *Hou and Wu* [1997] and *MacLachlan and Moulton* [2006]. In line with multigrid principles, it is recognized that the fine system information relates to different length scales, and a hierarchy of coarse models is needed to preserve it. The assumption behind these methods is a high level of confidence in the correctness of the fine scale model. The

suggested approach, instead, attempts to focus on the large scale behaviour of the system, in the belief that uncertainty on the fine details is likely to reduce the benefit of a more accurate coarsening.

It must be stressed that the choice of renormalization scheme greatly affects the suitability of the method for different scenarios. In the present work a renormalization scheme will be suggested with the aim of preserving the features of the pressure profile.

2.2. The Haar wavelet matrix. A very useful tool in the analysis of systems with an emphasis on scale is provided by wavelet transforms [Daubechies, 1992]. Similar to Fourier transforms, these can be used to express data as a combination of different basis functions with a specific coefficient, but allowing for resolution both in space and frequency. Wavelets have been used in the context of up-scaling, mainly as a filtering procedure to eliminate fluctuations in the permeability field [Ebrahimi and Sahimi, 2004].

The present method, however, attempts to transform the equations relating permeability and pressure and was inspired by the application of wavelets in the coarsening of coupling matrices in the Ising model [Ismail et al., 2003, 2005]. In this paper we will only use results for the Haar wavelet, the simplest kind of wavelet which separates the mean of the data from the fluctuations. However, the formalism introduced is valid independent of the type of wavelet and future work will explore other possible choices.

A family of wavelets can be constructed through the scaling and shifting of the so called mother wavelet: $\psi_{jk}(x) \equiv \psi(2^{j/2}x - k)$, where $\psi(x)$ is the mother wavelet, $j \in \mathbb{Z}$ is the scale parameter and k is the shift. In matrix form,

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

For example, if we apply this transform to a 2×1 vector we can obtain a new vector in terms of averages and differences of the original values. As will be seen in section 3.2, this procedure is at the heart of the suggested renormalization scheme. A useful property of \mathbf{H} is that its transpose is proportional to its inverse, which allows us to substitute the calculation of its inverse with a simple matrix multiplication.

3. A METHOD FOR COARSENING PERMEABILITY

3.1. The system. The simple system that will be considered is a 1-D array of cells in which permeability is defined for each cell and a pressure difference is imposed between the left and right boundaries. In the case of horizontal viscosity dominated laminar flow of a single fluid, the rate of flow \mathbf{q} is related to permeability K and pressure \mathbf{P} through Darcy's equation, $\mathbf{q} = -K\nabla\mathbf{P}$, which combined with flow conservation, $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} = 0$, gives $\nabla \cdot (K\nabla\mathbf{P}) = 0$. After Settari [1979], a finite difference discretization of the problem with permeability defined at the cell centres and pressure being piece-wise linear across the cell boundary leads to inter-cell transmissibility t_{ij} being the harmonic average of the cell transmissibilities t_i and t_j , where $t_i = k_i/\Delta x$ and $\Delta x = 1$ for convenience. In this representation Darcy's law is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{TP} = \mathbf{R}, \tag{1}$$

\mathbf{T} being the transmissibility matrix, \mathbf{P} a pressure vector, and \mathbf{R} the boundary condition [King, 1996]. In one-, two-, and three-dimensional systems \mathbf{T} is as in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1. The structure of the transmissibility matrix \mathbf{T} for $N = 4$ in (a) $d = 1$, (b) $d = 2$, and (c) $d = 3$, reproduced from *Pancaldi et al.* [2006].

3.2. Pressure averaging and permeability coarsening. As anticipated in Section 1, it is possible to specify the coarsening method to the required result. For example, it would be interesting to know what permeability field would give rise to the average of the pressure field. Clearly this will entail losing details and smoothing out sharp features, but, up to the level of coarsening required in making the model computationally tractable, most of the information on the system will be preserved. A more detailed discussion can be found in *Pancaldi et al.* [2006].

Considering an $N \times 1$ pressure vector, with $N = 4$, the averages and fluctuations can be separated in the following way:

$$\mathbf{P}' = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{P} = \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma \\ \Delta \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{W} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{P} = \begin{bmatrix} p_1 \\ p_2 \\ p_3 \\ p_4 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \Sigma = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{p_1 + p_2}{2} \\ \frac{p_3 + p_4}{2} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \Delta = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{p_1 - p_2}{2} \\ \frac{p_3 - p_4}{2} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

Exploiting the fact that $\mathbf{W}\mathbf{W}^T = \mathbf{W}^T\mathbf{W}$ is equal to the identity divided by $1/n$, we can operate on Equation (1) to coarsen the system by a factor $n = 2$ as follows:

$$\mathbf{T}\mathbf{W}^T\mathbf{W}\mathbf{P} = \frac{1}{n}\mathbf{R} \Leftrightarrow (\mathbf{W}\mathbf{T}\mathbf{W}^T)\mathbf{W}\mathbf{P} = \frac{1}{n}\mathbf{W}\mathbf{R}, \quad (4)$$

defining the transformed variables $\mathbf{T}' = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{T}\mathbf{W}^T$, $\mathbf{P}' = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{P}$, $\mathbf{R}' = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{R}$ we have

$$\mathbf{T}'\mathbf{P}' = \frac{1}{n}\mathbf{R}'. \quad (5)$$

To obtain an exact solution for the average pressure in the coarse scale, Δ should be eliminated in Equation (5) leaving an expression only in Σ . While this is straight forward in one dimension, it is not so in higher dimensions. A possible alternative is to ignore the fluctuations Δ , or equivalently to assume the matrix \mathbf{T}' to be block diagonal.

To do this, we define new variables \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{R} composed of the first $(N/2)$ elements of \mathbf{P}' and \mathbf{R}' respectively, and \mathcal{T} as the $(N/2) \times (N/2)$ upper left corner of \mathbf{T}' :

$$\mathbf{T}' = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B^T & C \end{bmatrix}; \quad \mathcal{T} = A = \begin{bmatrix} 2k_1 + t_{23} & -t_{23} \\ -t_{23} & t_{23} + 2k_4 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

FIGURE 2. A schematic representation of cell and block permeabilities and transmissibilities. **(a-left)** A 32×32 permeability map. **(a-right)** The 16×16 coarsened permeability map. A 4×4 group of cells is substituted by a 2×2 group of blocks. **(b-left)** Blow-up of a 4×4 group of cells. **(b-right)** Blow-up of a 2×2 group of blocks. Properties of cells are subscripted with numbers, properties of blocks with letters. Permeabilities are indicated by k and transmissibilities with t , $k_A = (k_1 + k_2)/2$, $t_{AB} = (t_{23} + t_{67})/2$, $t_{AC} = (t_{59} + t_{610})/2$.

$$\mathcal{TP} = \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{R}; \mathcal{P} = \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{T}^{-1}\mathcal{R}; \mathbf{P}_{coarse} = 2\mathcal{P}. \quad (7)$$

This corresponds to performing a mean-field approximation, where fluctuations are ignored with the intent to concentrate on the large scale behaviour of the system. To determine the coarse pressure, we invert the renormalized transmissibility matrix \mathcal{T} and multiply the resulting pressure by 2. The rescale is necessary to compensate for the change from cell values to block values, which has doubled the size of Δx .

A similar treatment can be applied to two- and three-dimensional systems, the only differences being in the structure of the \mathbf{W} matrix and in the rescaling factor.

3.3. A renormalization scheme. Comparing the elements in \mathcal{T} to the elements in the transmissibility matrix of a system with a smaller number of cells provides a renormalization scheme that can be implemented as a fast up-scaling method, see Figure 2 and *Pancaldi et al.* [2006] and appendix within.

3.4. Numerical simulations. To assess the error introduced in making the mean-field approximation, permeability data sets were generated in two and three dimensions, see *Pancaldi et al.* [2006] for details on the method. Results are presented for two-dimensional systems for simplicity. As can be seen in Figure 3, the absolute relative error between the coarse pressure obtained in the mean-field approximation and the averaged pressure is of order 10^{-3} . It can be shown that even in extremely heterogeneous systems, where permeability spans over 14 orders of magnitude, the renormalization scheme suggested reproduces the pressure average within errors of about 20% [*Pancaldi et al.*, 2006].

A further qualitative test on the accuracy of the coarsening method was performed by calculating the streamlines for one of the permeability maps. To this end, a fluid source and sink were positioned at the corners of the system and, as can be seen in Figure 4, even a coarsening of a factor 16 in each direction preserves the flow lines.

FIGURE 3. Wavelet renormalization of a permeability map from 32×32 to 16×16 . **(a1)** Fine scale permeability. **(a2)** Fine scale pressure solution obtained from fine scale permeability. **(a3)** Average of the fine scale pressure solution (2×2 cells averaged). **(b1)** Wavelet renormalized coarse permeability. **(b2)** Coarse pressure solution obtained from coarse permeability. **(b3)** Relative error, $(a3 - b2)/a3$. In this case the relative difference between the averaged fine scale pressure **(a3)** and the coarse pressure **(b2)** is within 2% and there is no evident bias towards over- or under-estimation.

FIGURE 4. Comparison of streamlines overlaid on permeability maps for a 256×256 system up-scaled to 16×16 . **(a)** System of linear size 256. **(b)** System up-scaled with wavelet method, 64×64 . **(c)** System up-scaled with wavelet method, 16×16 . Blue streamlines represent long Time Of Flight, red streamlines short TOF. The density of the streamlines is proportional to the magnitude of the flow.

4. TOWARDS TWO-PHASE FLOW

4.1. The saturation equation. To show the generality of the method presented we apply the mean-field approximation to a particular discretization of the advection equation, which could lead to insights in two-phase flow saturation equations.

We consider a one-dimensional homogeneous system with zero saturation and a source of constant saturation S_0 at the left boundary. The general solution is a step function propagating in time and space. After *King and Neuweiler* [2002], we can perform a

Laplace transform in time to obtain a matrix representation of the saturation equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t S(x, t) + u \partial_x S(x, t) &= 0, \\ \partial_t S_i(t) + \alpha \Delta_{ij} S_j(t) &= 0, \\ p S_i(p) + \alpha \Delta_{ij} S_j(p) - S_i(t=0) &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where Δ_{ij} is the centred finite difference spatial derivative, $\alpha = u/2\Delta x$ and $S_i(t=0) = 0$. We can notice the similarity between this problem and Equation (1):

$$\mathbf{MS} = \mathbf{R}; \mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} p & \alpha & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ -\alpha & p & \alpha & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & -\alpha & p & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \cdots & \cdots & -\alpha & p \end{bmatrix}; \mathbf{S} = \begin{bmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ \cdots \\ S_N \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{R} is simply a boundary condition and $R_i = \delta_{i,1}\alpha S_0$. We then proceed to define $\mathbf{M}' = \mathbf{WMW}^T$ and taking the mean-field approximation as in Section 3.2 we define \mathcal{M} and use it to calculate an approximation to the saturation average.

$$\mathcal{M} = \begin{bmatrix} p & \alpha/2 & 0 \\ -\alpha/2 & p & \alpha/2 \\ \cdots & \cdots & \cdots \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

In this mean-field approximation, the coarse system is found to exhibit advective motion with half the original speed. In principle, the method described can be applied when u is position dependent, a system which is closer to the Buckley-Leverett problem. However, it is foreseeable that the mean-field approximation will be less successful for an inhomogeneous system. Preliminary numerical simulations have shown that at least at constant time the spatial profile of saturation can be coarsened accurately in the mean-field approximation.

4.2. Beyond the mean-field approach. Given the simplicity of the homogeneous system in one dimension, it is possible to solve for the average saturation exactly and also to express the coarse operator as a combination of the mean-field result plus a correction:

$$\mathbf{M}' = \begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ -B & A^T \end{bmatrix}; \mathbf{S}' = \mathbf{WS} = \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma \\ \Delta \end{bmatrix}, (\mathbf{A} + \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{A}^T)^{-1}\mathbf{B}) \Sigma = \mathbf{R}'. \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{R}' is a transformed boundary condition. Further work will explore the time evolution of the system.

5. CONCLUSION AND FURTHER APPLICATIONS

A block renormalization coarsening method based on Haar wavelets was presented and applied to permeability up-scaling and coarsening of the advection equation. While not requiring the calculation of fluxes, unlike many successful coarsening methods, this technique ensures a close match between the obtained pressure field and the average of the original pressure and is shown to preserve the streamline structure in a tracer flow experiment.

The application of the formalism to the coarsening of the advection equation highlights its wide applicability and suggests the possibility of treating two-phase flow problems.

Although the above results refer to cartesian grid finite difference models, a useful up-scaling method should be successful independent of the geometry of the problem. In the case of corner point geometry grids, where the coordination number of each node is still constant and equal to $2d$ in d dimensions, only a re-definition of inter-cell transmissibilities is required, the structure of \mathbf{T} being maintained. Furthermore, the use of different wavelets might improve the performance of the mean-field approximation and further analysis might suggest a way to include the fluctuation terms so far discarded.

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